

1 **Microbial competition reduces interaction distances to the low μm -range**

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18 **Abstract**

19 Metabolic interactions between cells affect microbial community compositions and hence
20 their function in ecosystems. It is well-known that under competition for the exchanged
21 metabolite, concentration gradients constrain the distances over which interactions can occur.
22 However, interaction distances are typically quantified in two-dimensional systems or
23 without accounting for competition or other metabolite-removal, conditions which may not
24 very often match natural ecosystems. We here analyze the impact of cell-to-cell distance on
25 unidirectional cross-feeding in a three-dimensional system with competition for the
26 exchanged metabolite. Effective interaction distances were computed with a reaction-
27 diffusion model and experimentally verified by growing a synthetic consortium of 1 μm -
28 sized metabolite producer, receiver and competitor cells in different spatial structures. We
29 show that receivers cannot interact with producers $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$ away from them, as product
30 concentration gradients flatten close to producer cells. We developed an aggregation protocol
31 and created variants of the receiver cells' import system, to show that within producer-
32 receiver aggregates even low affinity receiver cells could interact with producers. These
33 results show that competition or other metabolite-removal of a public good in a three-
34 dimensional system reduces the interaction distance to the low micrometer-range,
35 highlighting the importance of concentration gradients as physical constraint for cellular
36 interactions.

37 **Introduction**

38 Microbial interactions are observed in dense biofilms (0 μm between cells) as well as in
39 oceans (>100 μm between cells), demonstrating that cells interact at various distances [1–4].

40 These interactions influence the selection pressure within an environment, and therefore
41 affect the structure and evolution of microbial communities [5]. As these communities play
42 an important role in many ecosystems, from global biogeochemical fluxes [6] to human
43 health [7], understanding and controlling these interactions is of high importance.

44

45 Metabolites or signaling molecules involved in interactions can be exchanged via contact-
46 dependent and contact-independent transfer mechanisms. Contact-dependent mechanisms
47 require short cell-to-cell distances and use for instance direct contact between cells, vesicle
48 chains or nanotubes for exchange [5]. Contact-independent mechanisms require passive or
49 active transport of the produced compound to the extracellular space, where it subsequently
50 moves via diffusion and convection [5]. Contact-independent interactions can be local
51 (mainly between neighboring cells) or global (within the whole population), depending on the
52 profile of the concentration gradient. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* for instance uses its
53 extracellular enzyme invertase to split sucrose, resulting in a glucose and fructose gradient
54 around the cell. At high sucrose concentrations both aggregated and single yeast cells can
55 grow (global interactions), while at low sucrose concentrations only aggregated yeast cells
56 grow (local interactions) [8]. A similar pattern is observed for the extracellular protease of
57 *Lactococcus lactis*, which activity results in a peptide gradient around the cell. At high cell
58 densities both protease positive and protease negative cells grow, while at low cell densities
59 mainly protease positive cells grow, since only they can benefit from their produced peptides
60 [9].

61

62 Whether contact-independent interactions are local or global depends on the distance between
63 cells and the concentration gradient profile, which is affected by the metabolite source, the
64 metabolite-sink and the diffusion and convection rate between them. The metabolite source
65 can for instance be a producer cell [10], a nutrient pool in the environment [11] or an
66 extracellular enzyme [8, 9]. The metabolite-sink can be a metabolite consuming cell [12, 13],
67 a metabolite degrading enzyme [14] or the volume of the system, as dilution reduces the
68 metabolite concentration [8, 9]. Although the exact nature of the source and sink are often
69 only implicitly mentioned in these studies, their importance is well-known. Costly
70 cooperative interactions are for instance more likely to evolve when cells are close to each
71 other, because cooperators compete with wildtype non-cooperators for the excreted
72 metabolite [5, 15, 16]. Selection for interactions is therefore often done by co-culturing cells
73 on agar plates [17–19], and it is also described that interacting cells evolved aggregating
74 phenotypes [20].

75

76 These examples show that in the presence of a metabolite-removing sink, concentration
77 gradients constrain the distances over which interactions can occur. It is however not clear at
78 what distances such interactions occur. Previous studies either quantified these distances in
79 two-dimensional systems [11–13] or without a metabolite-removing sink [13, 14], while
80 natural microbial communities reside in three-dimensional environments in which competing
81 metabolite consumers and other types of metabolite-removing sinks are very likely to be
82 present. We therefore combined computational and experimental analyses to provide a more
83 systematic and quantitative perspective on the impact of cell-to-cell distance on metabolic
84 interactions in three dimensions and in the presence of metabolite-removing sinks. The
85 reaction-diffusion model and experimental results show that in these conditions receiver cells
86 fixed at $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$ from glucose producing cells cannot interact with the producer cells, while

87 producer-receiver aggregation facilitates metabolic interactions even when receiver cells have
88 a low affinity for the product caused by genetic variation of their glucose import systems.
89 These results suggest that competition or other metabolite-removal in a three-dimensional
90 system reduces interaction distances to well below 15 μm .
91

92 **Materials and methods**

93 **Strains and media**

94 All the strains that were used are listed in Table 1. *Lactococcus lactis* NZ9000 strains
95 PTSman_GFP, PTScel_GFP, and glcU_GFP were obtained by a single-crossover integration
96 of vector pSEUDO::*Pusp45-gfp* [21] into the *pseudo* 10 locus on the chromosome of *L. lactis*
97 NZ9000 Δ *ptcC* Δ *glcU*, NZ9000 Δ *ptnABCD* Δ *glcU*, and NZ9000 Δ *ptnABCD* Δ *ptcC* [22],
98 respectively. Integration was performed as previously described [23]. Transformants were
99 selected on M17-agar plates supplemented with glucose, sucrose and 5 μ g/mL erythromycin.

100

101 *L. lactis* was grown in chemically defined medium (CDM) described by Otto *et al.* [24], with
102 the following changes: 0.6 g/L NH₄-citrate, 2.5 mg/L biotin, 0.02 mg/L riboflavin and no
103 folic acid. *L. lactis* NZ9000 Glc-Lac⁺ was pre-cultured in CDM + 0.95 wt% lactose, *L. lactis*
104 MG5267 in CDM + 0.5 wt% lactose and *L. lactis* MG1363 [25], *L. lactis* MG1363_GFP, *L.*
105 *lactis* NZ9000_GFP_PTSman, *L. lactis* NZ9000_GFP_glcU and *L. lactis*
106 NZ9000_GFP_PTScel in CDM + 0.5 wt% glucose. Agarose beads contained CDM + 0.4
107 wt% carbon source and were incubated surrounded by oil, or by CDM + 0.2 wt% carbon
108 source. Mono-cultures were incubated with the same carbon source as their pre-culture, co-
109 cultures were incubated in presence of lactose. Incubations were done at 30°C.

110

111 **Table 1. Bacterial strains and plasmids used in this study**

<i>L. lactis</i> strain	Description	Reference
NZ9000 Δ <i>ptcCΔ<i>glcU</i></i>	Derivative of NZ9000 containing a 1254 bp deletion in <i>ptcC</i> and a 864 bp deletion in <i>glcU</i> .	[22]
NZ9000 Δ <i>ptnABCDΔ<i>glcU</i></i>	Derivative of NZ9000 containing a 1736 bp deletion in <i>ptnABCD</i> and a 864 bp deletion in <i>glcU</i> .	[22]
NZ9000 Δ <i>ptnABCDΔ<i>ptcC</i></i>	Derivative of NZ9000 containing a 1736 bp deletion in <i>ptnABCD</i> and a 1254 bp deletion in <i>ptcC</i> .	[22]
MG5267	<i>L. lactis</i> MG1363 with the lactose operon integrated into the genome.	[26]
NZ9000 Glc-Lac+	NZ9000 Δ <i>glk</i> Δ <i>ptnABCD</i> containing a 657-bp deletion in <i>ptcBA</i> , carrying pMG8020 (lactose mini-plasmid of 23.7 kb, containing <i>lacFEGABCD</i> , derivative of pLP712).	[27]
MG1363_GFP	MG1363 carrying pSEUDO:: <i>P_{usp45}-gfp</i> .	[21]
NZ9000_PTS _{man} _GFP	Ery ^r , NZ9000 Δ <i>ptcCΔ<i>glcU</i> carrying pSEUDO::<i>P_{usp45}-gfp</i>.</i>	This work
NZ9000_PTS _{cel} _GFP	Ery ^r , NZ9000 Δ <i>ptnABCDΔ<i>glcU</i> carrying pSEUDO::<i>P_{usp45}-gfp</i>.</i>	This work
NZ9000_glcU_GFP	Ery ^r , NZ9000 Δ <i>ptnABCDΔ<i>ptcC</i> carrying pSEUDO::<i>P_{usp45}-gfp</i>.</i>	This work
Plasmids	Description	Reference
pSEUDO:: <i>P_{usp45}-gfp</i>	Ery ^r , integration vector, pSEUDO:: <i>P_{usp45}-sfgfp(Bs)</i> derivative, carrying the gene coding for the green fluorescent protein (Dasher-GFP).	[21]

112

113 **Aggregation protocol**

114 Producer and receiver cell pre-cultures (10 mL) were washed three times with 0.9% sodium
115 chloride. Receiver cells were resuspended in 2 mL 0.225% sodium chloride, producer cells
116 were resuspended in 0.9% sodium chloride and diluted to an OD₆₀₀ of 1.1. Both were
117 incubated in an ultrasonification bath (Branson 200 Ultrasonic cleaner, Branson Ultrasonics,
118 Danbury, CT, USA) at 46 kHz for 3 minutes to ensure complete resuspension to single cells.
119 The surface of (non-)producer cells was charged positively by electrostatic deposition of
120 polyethyleneimine (PEI; Mr 600 000 - 1 000 000; ~50% in H₂O; Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis,
121 MO, USA) as follows. Sonicated producer cells were mixed with 0.25% PEI (hydrated, pH 7)
122 in a 1:1 (v/v) ratio and incubated at room temperature for 5 minutes. After incubation cells
123 were collected by centrifugation (900 g, 3 minutes) and washed by replacing the supernatant
124 with 0.9% sodium chloride five times without resuspending the pellet. Washed cells were
125 resuspended in 200 µL 0.9% sodium chloride and sonicated as described above. The surface
126 of washed receiver cells was negatively charged and therefore not further modified [28]. Cell
127 concentrations in the prepared producer and receiver suspensions were measured with flow
128 cytometry (Accuri C6, BD Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA).

129 Aggregates were formed electrostatically by mixing the positively charged producer cells
130 with the negatively charged receiver cells, such that the oppositely charged cells stuck to each
131 other. The suspension with negatively charged receiver cells was mixed using a T10 basic
132 ULTRA TURRAX homogenizer with an S10N-5G dispersing element (IKA, Staufen,
133 Germany) at 8000 rpm for 15-20 minutes. While mixing, the positively charged producer
134 cells were added to the negatively charged receiver cells using a 1 mL syringe (Terumo,
135 Tokyo, Japan), a Chemyx Fusion 200 syringe pump (125-400 µL/h, Chemyx Inc., Stafford,
136 TX, USA) and polyethylene tubing (inner diameter 0.38 mm, BD, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA).

137 The mixing time (15-20 minutes) and syringe pump flow rate (125-400 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$) were adjusted
138 within the mentioned ranges such that the final aggregate percentage was $\sim 3\%$.

139

140 **Agarose beads formation and analysis**

141 Agarose beads in oil were made by mixing a water and an oil phase. The oil phase contained
142 Novec HFE 7500 fluorinated oil (3M, Maplewood, MN, USA) and 0.2% PicoSurf 1
143 surfactant (Sphere Fluidics, Cambridge, UK). The water phase contained CDM, 1 wt%
144 melted agarose with ultra-low gelling temperature (Type IX-A, A2576, Sigma-Aldrich, Saint
145 Louis, MO, USA) and cells, and it was prepared as follows. Pre-cultures were washed with
146 phosphate buffered saline (PBS) and the OD_{600} was measured to determine the cell
147 concentration (assuming $\text{OD } 1 = 10^9$ cells/mL). The total cell concentration in the aggregate
148 suspension was determined using flow cytometry (Accuri C6). The producer cell or aggregate
149 concentration in CDM with agarose was set to $2.7 \cdot 10^6/\text{mL}$, the receiver cell concentration to
150 $8.9 \cdot 10^7$ cells/mL.

151 300 μL water phase and 700 μL oil phase were mixed using a T10 basic ULTRA TURRAX
152 homogenizer with an S10N-5G dispersing element at 8000 rpm for 5 minutes. Emulsions
153 were subsequently placed on ice for at least 20 minutes, to solidify the agarose beads. After
154 solidification cells could not move and growth therefore resulted in micro-colony formation
155 within the agarose bead. Formed agarose beads had an average diameter of 37 μm
156 (supplementary information, section 1). Based on this average diameter, each bead contained
157 on average 8 receiver cells. In addition to the receivers, $\sim 2\%$ of the beads contained two or
158 more producer cells/aggregates and $\sim 19\%$ contained one producer cell/aggregate ($\sim 79\%$
159 contained no producer/aggregate).

160

161 To incubate agarose beads in CDM, 1 mL CDM and 1 mL perfluorooctanol (PFO, Alfa
162 Aesar, Ward Hill, MA, USA) were added to the emulsion after solidification. This leads to
163 the breaking of the emulsion and separation of the water and oil phase upon gently mixing.
164 Subsequently the water phase, containing agarose beads in CDM, was separated from the oil
165 phase and incubated while rotating. For incubation in presence of competing glucose-
166 consumers 10^9 *L. lactis* MG1363 cells per mL were added to the CDM surrounding the
167 agarose beads (supplementary information, section 2).

168

169 Growth in agarose beads was analyzed with flow cytometry (Accuri C6). Agarose beads in
170 CDM were measured directly. For agarose beads in oil the emulsion was first broken by
171 adding 240 μ L PBS and 300 μ L PFO to 60 μ L emulsion, followed by gently mixing. The
172 water phase, containing agarose beads in PBS, was separated from the oil phase and
173 measured using flow cytometry. Details about the flow cytometry gating strategy and data
174 analysis are shown in supplementary information section 3.

175

176 **Three-dimensional reaction-diffusion model**

177 A three-dimensional, numerical reaction-diffusion model was implemented in COMSOL
178 Multiphysics (COMSOL 5.0, Comsol Inc., Burlington, MA, USA). Two spherical agarose
179 beads were placed in a cubic computational domain. One bead contained a producer cell that
180 secreted glucose with a constant rate, and both beads contained eight receiver cells that
181 consumed glucose based on Monod (saturation) kinetics. The concentration at the agarose
182 bead surface resulted from a partition coefficient which was set to 0 to model incubation in
183 oil, and to 1 to model incubation in CDM. The diffusion coefficient of glucose was set to
184 $6.7 \cdot 10^{-10}$ m^2/s [29] both inside and outside agarose beads [30], and 10 times lower in micro-
185 colonies [29, 31]. A time-dependent study yielded the spatial distribution of glucose. See

186 supplementary information section 4 for more details about the geometry and used
187 parameters.

188 **Results**

189 **Reaction-diffusion modelling predicts short interaction distances in three-dimensional** 190 **systems**

191 To compare concentration gradients in two- and three-dimensional systems we made
192 reaction-diffusion models in COMSOL Multiphysics (supplementary information, section
193 4.2). The concentration gradients around a producer cell were calculated either in cube to
194 mimic a three-dimensional system, or in a thin plate to mimic a two-dimensional system
195 (plate thickness of 1.1 μm , roughly matching the producer cell diameter of 1 μm). In both
196 cases the total volume was 1 nL (10^6 cells/mL). The model predicted that in the thin plate the
197 maximal concentration is halved at 24 μm from the producer cell, while in the cube this
198 distance is 0.6 μm (Figure S5). This indicated that in three-dimensional systems the distances
199 at which cells can interact are significantly shorter than in two-dimensional systems.

200

201 **Design of a synthetic consortium and three-dimensional spatial structure for growth**

202 To study how concentration gradients constrain interactions between micro-organisms in a
203 three-dimensional environment, we extended the cubic model to contain producer and
204 receiver cells, and analyzed the impact of cell-to-cell distance on the interaction
205 (supplementary information, section 4.3). To experimentally validate the model results we
206 constructed synthetic consortia using four *L. lactis* strains. 1) A “producer” that takes up
207 lactose and hydrolyzes it intracellularly to glucose and galactose. It was engineered to not
208 metabolize glucose, which was therefore secreted while the cells grew on galactose. 2) A
209 GFP-expressing “receiver” that can take up and grow on glucose, but not lactose. 3) A “non-
210 producer” that takes up lactose. It uses both the glucose and galactose moiety for growth, and
211 therefore does not secrete glucose. 4) A “competing glucose-consumer” (Figure 1A). To co-
212 culture these cells in a three-dimensional system, glucose-producers and -receivers (the

213 unidirectional cross-feeders) were encapsulated in solidified agarose beads with an average
214 diameter of ~40 μm . For negative controls, glucose-producers were replaced by glucose-
215 “non-producers”. Cells were embedded in the beads either as separate cells (~15 μm between
216 cells) or as aggregates (0 μm between cells) (Figure 1B). During incubation agarose beads
217 were separated either by oil or by CDM (Figure 1C). Separation by oil prevented diffusion of
218 glucose from beads, enabling us to validate that cells can grow and interact in agarose beads.
219 Separation by CDM resulted in glucose diffusion from beads, enabling us to study
220 unidirectional cross-feeding in presence of a concentration gradient in a three-dimensional
221 system. To investigate the effect of metabolite-removal on the interaction distances,
222 interactions were analyzed in presence and absence of competing glucose-consumers outside
223 the beads (Figure 1C).
224

A. Synthetic consortium

B. Spatial structure within beads

C. Spatial structure between beads

agarose beads surrounded by oil
no diffusion from beads

agarose beads surrounded by CDM
diffusion from beads

226 **Figure 1. Metabolic interactions in three-dimensional spatially structured environments. (A)**

227 The four *L. lactis* strains that were used to make synthetic consortia: 1) “producers” which take up
228 lactose and secrete glucose, 2) “receivers” which take up glucose and express GFP, 3) “non-
229 producers” which take up lactose but do not secrete glucose and 4) “competing glucose-consumers”
230 which take up glucose (supplementary information, section 2). **(B)** The three-dimensional spatial
231 structure within agarose beads. A distance of 15 μm between cells is comparable to a homogeneous
232 distribution of $3 \cdot 10^8$ bacteria/mL. For visibility reasons the microscope picture shows a GFP-
233 expressing cell surrounded by non-fluorescent cells. Aggregates used in experiments were formed
234 oppositely: a (non-)producer cell was surrounded by GFP-expressing receivers. **(C)** The three-
235 dimensional spatial structure between agarose beads. Aggregates were only incubated in presence of
236 competing glucose-consumers.

237

238 To analyze if we could detect growth in agarose beads we cultured producers and receivers in
239 beads surrounded by oil (no glucose diffusion from beads) and analyzed the beads with flow
240 cytometry before and after incubation. Beads inoculated with mono-cultures of producers
241 (lactose as carbon source) or receivers (glucose as carbon source) showed an increased
242 forward scatter after incubation, indicating that cells could grow inside beads. In agreement
243 with our expectation the fluorescence/scatter ratio of beads with growth was low for beads
244 with producers and high for beads with GFP-expressing receivers (Figure 2B).

245 To validate that cells could also interact within beads, we made beads such that ~21% of
246 them contained both a producer and receivers and ~79% contained receivers only. Because
247 the metabolic interaction is unidirectional, we expected that in presence of lactose the
248 producers would always grow, while the receivers would only grow when glucose, secreted
249 by producers, was available to them (Figure 2A). After incubation $14 \pm 1\%$ of the agarose
250 beads showed an increased forward scatter, and these beads had a high fluorescence/scatter

251 ratio (Figure 2B, Table 2). This is close to the expected 21% of beads with producer and
252 receivers, indicating that receivers could only grow in beads with producers.
253 Together this setup forms a synthetic consortium where spatial interactions can be
254 manipulated in a three-dimensional environment, and which allows the detection of growth
255 and interactions using flow cytometry.

256

257 **Under glucose competition receivers cannot interact with producers ~15 μm away**

258 In the example above glucose could not diffuse from beads and each agarose bead acted as an
259 individual compartment. In contrast, when glucose can diffuse from agarose beads the model
260 predicted that the glucose concentration flattens close to the producer. In that case receivers
261 at a distance of 15 μm from a producer in the same bead are exposed to similar glucose
262 concentrations as receivers in beads without a producer (Figure 2C). If this prediction was
263 correct, we expected that most receivers can grow when the global glucose concentration
264 builds up, while in case of glucose competition the glucose concentration stays low and even
265 receivers 15 μm away from a producer in the same bead should not be able to grow. We
266 therefore incubated agarose beads in CDM, which allows glucose diffusion from beads.
267 Without competing glucose-consumers in the CDM outside the beads $75\pm 7\%$ of the beads
268 showed growth and these beads had a high fluorescence/scatter ratio (Figure 2D, Table 2).
269 This indicates growth of both receivers with and receivers without a producer in their bead.
270 When we took the same beads but added competing glucose-consumers outside the beads,
271 only $15\pm 3\%$ of the beads contained growth. In the beads where growth was observed the
272 fluorescence/scatter ratio was low, indicating that only producers grew (Figure 2D, Table 2).
273 These results are consistent with the model predictions and show that under glucose
274 competition receivers cannot interact with producers even if they are only ~15 μm away.

275

276 Without competing glucose-consumers still $25\pm 7\%$ of the beads were gated as “no growth”,
277 although the model predicted that all receivers could grow (Figure 2C and 2D). These beads
278 could be false negatives caused by our conservative gating strategy, or by empty beads with
279 single fluorescent cells attached to their outside. Conversely, for the beads gated as “growth”,
280 we observed an increased fluorescence/scatter ratio compared to the single receiver controls
281 (Figure 2D). It is known that fluorescence of individual cells increases with decreasing
282 growth rate [32, 33], suggesting that in co-cultures the higher fluorescence/scatter ratio could
283 be caused by glucose limited and therefore slower growth of the receivers in the beads.
284 Together this data shows that competition for glucose in a three-dimensional environment
285 prevents interactions at $\sim 15\ \mu\text{m}$ distance, because the presence of competing public good-
286 consumers leads to steep concentration gradients.

287

288 **Aggregated producers and receivers interact even under glucose competition**

289 In the presence of steep concentration gradients microbial interactions might be facilitated by
290 bringing producers and receivers in close proximity. Consistently, the model predicted that
291 cell aggregation would allow receivers to grow under glucose competition (Figure 2E). We
292 developed a protocol to make producer-receiver aggregates. Defined aggregates were formed
293 by adding positively charged producers to an excess of negatively charged receivers, ensuring
294 that producers were directly surrounded by receivers. In this way we obtained a mixture of
295 single receivers and aggregates of one producer and approximately eight receivers (Figure
296 1B). We aimed to add an aggregate to $\sim 21\%$ of the beads, but we could only roughly estimate
297 the aggregate concentration in the mixture based on the added amount of positively charged
298 cells. However, underestimating this percentage would not affect the results, as we only
299 analyze agarose beads with growth after incubation (supplementary information, section 3).

300 We incubated the formed agarose beads in CDM with competing glucose-consumers and
 301 after incubation we saw an increased scatter in $3 \pm 2\%$ of the beads (Figure 2F, Table 2),
 302 indicating only growth in beads with both producers and receivers. The fluorescence/scatter
 303 ratio of beads with growth was increased compared to the producer mono-culture (Figure 2F),
 304 indicating growth of both producers and receivers. Beads with grown aggregates of non-
 305 producers and receivers showed a fluorescence/scatter ratio similar to the producer mono-
 306 culture (Figure 2F), indicating that the aggregation protocol or the data analysis procedure did
 307 not influence the readout.

308 Therefore, the results show that cell aggregation facilitates microbial interactions, even in a
 309 three-dimensional system with competition for the public good.

310

311 **Table 2. Consortium response in different spatial structures.** Summary of the experimental results

312 of Figure 2.

incubation condition	cell-to-cell distance	producer + receivers (~21%) receivers only (~79%)		non-producer + receivers (~21%) receivers only (~79%)	
		beads with growth	fluorescence/ scatter ratio	beads with growth	fluorescence/ scatter ratio
no diffusion from beads	~15 μm	$14 \pm 1\%$	High	$16 \pm 0\%$	Low
diffusion from beads, no competing glucose consumers	~15 μm	$75 \pm 7\%$	High	$6 \pm 1\%$	Low
diffusion from beads, competing glucose consumers	~15 μm	$15 \pm 3\%$	Low	$9 \pm 2\%$	Low
	0 μm	$3 \pm 2\%$	Medium	$4 \pm 2\%$	Low

313

314

315 **Figure 2. Consortium response in different spatial structures.** Panels (A), (C), and (E) show the
316 predicted concentration gradient at the diagonal of the cube, for the following spatial structure: (A)
317 No diffusion from beads, (C) Diffusion from beads, $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$ between cells within a bead and (E)
318 diffusion from beads, aggregated cells within a bead. In panels (B), (D) and (F) the experimental
319 results are shown for these different spatial structures. The forward scatter histograms show the
320 populations that were gated as “growth” in the producer-receiver co-cultures ($n=3$). From these
321 populations the fluorescence/scatter signal was determined. Next to the producer-receiver co-culture
322 control samples were included: receivers only, producers only and co-cultures of non-producers and
323 receivers ($n=3$ for each of them). The non-producers and receivers, and the producers only controls
324 are overlapping in all plots. The schematic drawing at the right is based on the experimental data and
325 shows which cells could grow in producer-receiver co-cultures.

326

327 **Aggregation results in dense micro-colonies, facilitating growth of receivers with low**
328 **affinity and low V_{max} glucose transporters**

329 To study the effect of glucose uptake efficiency on the receiver response, we modelled
330 producer-receiver aggregates with receivers that have glucose-transporters with different
331 affinities (K_m) and maximal uptake rates (V_{max}). Specifically, we modelled receivers that had
332 one of the three different glucose transporters of *L. lactis* [22] (supplementary information,
333 section 4.5). Within aggregates the effective diffusion coefficient ($D_{\text{eff},s}$) is described to be
334 10-70% of the diffusion coefficient in water (D_s), depending on the aggregates’ density [29,
335 31]. When we set $D_{\text{eff},s}$ to 10% of D_s , the model predicts that receivers with the low K_m and
336 high V_{max} transporter PTSman ($K_m = 0.013 \text{ mM}$, $V_{\text{max}} = 0.22 \mu\text{mol}/\text{min}/\text{mg protein}$) consume
337 about 90 times more glucose than receivers with a high K_m or low V_{max} transporter (PTScel:
338 $K_m = 8.7 \text{ mM}$, $V_{\text{max}} = 0.25 \mu\text{mol}/\text{min}/\text{mg protein}$, glcU: $K_m = 2.4 \text{ mM}$, $V_{\text{max}} = 0.08$
339 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}/\text{mg protein}$) (supplementary information, section 4.5). When $D_{\text{eff},s}$ is 70% of D_s ,
340 this difference is almost 350 fold.

341 As the model predicted less glucose consumption by receivers with low glucose affinities and
342 low maximal glucose uptake rates, we constitutively expressed GFP in three engineered *L.*
343 *lactis* NZ9000 strains which each contain only one of the three glucose transporters [27]. We
344 subsequently analyzed if their uptake was high enough to interact with producers. As we saw
345 before, the fluorescence/scatter ratio in mono-culture controls decreased with an increasing
346 growth rate (Figure 3 and supplementary information section 5). The data further show that in
347 producer-receiver aggregates even the low affinity receivers could grow and the differences
348 in fluorescence/scatter ratio between the mutants were small (2-3 fold). Based on the model
349 this data suggests that dense micro-colonies with a low $D_{\text{eff},s}$ were formed. Aggregates with
350 receivers containing the low K_m and high V_{max} transporter PTSman showed the highest
351 fluorescence/scatter ratio. Consistent with the model predictions this result suggests that
352 PTSman containing receivers have the highest glucose uptake rate.

353 Altogether the data show that in a three-dimensional system with a metabolite consuming
354 sink a steep concentration gradient is obtained, and cells only ~15 μm away from each other
355 cannot interact through glucose cross-feeding. This physical constraint can be overcome by
356 bringing cells together in the low micrometer range, as achieved through cell aggregation -
357 physical contact.

358

Figure 3. Effect of glucose transporter affinity and V_{max} on the receiver response. Mono- and co-cultures of (non-)producers and receivers with different glucose transporters were incubated in agarose beads surrounded by CDM. **(A)** Producer mono-cultures were incubated in presence of lactose, receiver mono-cultures in presence of glucose. Agarose beads contained separated cells. **(B)** Co-cultures were incubated in presence of lactose. Agarose beads contained either separated cells (~15 μm between cells within a bead), or producer-receiver aggregates (0 μm between cells). The beads were incubated in CDM with and without competing glucose-consumers. For each culture the median and standard error of the median of the fluorescence/scatter ratio is shown (n=3). Receivers are ordered based on their growth rate (supplementary information section 5).

381 **Discussion**

382 Contact-independent interactions can be local or global, depending on the profile of the
383 concentration gradient. Previous studies quantified interaction distances either in monolayers
384 of cells (two-dimensional system) or in absence of a competing metabolite-sink [13, 14].
385 While these studies give valuable insight, they have a limited resemblance to natural
386 ecosystems, which are typically three-dimensional and harbor competing organisms and other
387 metabolite-removing sinks. A reaction-diffusion model predicted that in three-dimensional
388 systems the concentration gradient drops much faster than in two-dimensional systems (the
389 maximal concentration is halved at 0.6 μm instead of 24 μm), suggesting that in natural
390 ecosystems interaction ranges might be much shorter than the *in vitro* two-dimensional
391 systems predict. To better understand how concentration gradient constraints affect the
392 composition and fitness of natural communities, we analyzed the impact of cell-to-cell
393 distance on unidirectional cross-feeding in three dimensions in the presence and absence of a
394 competing metabolite consumer as a public good-removing sink.

395

396 Without competing glucose-consumers we observed a global response: receivers grew at all
397 distances from producers (Figure 2D, Table 2). When we added competing glucose-
398 consumers only receivers aggregated with producers could grow (Figure 2D and 2F, Table 2).
399 Diener *et al.* observed a similar pattern of local and global interactions during *S. cerevisiae*
400 mating [14]. Haploid cells secrete a peptide, which is sensed and degraded by haploid cells of
401 the opposite mating type. This results in a local high peptide concentration and local
402 interactions: cells from opposite mating types initiate mating specifically in each other's
403 direction. However, incubation of mutants that could not degrade the peptide resulted in a
404 global high peptide concentration, and independent of their location cells initiated mating in
405 different directions. For wildtype cells Diener *et al.* predicted that the maximum information

406 content of the peptide distribution is similar for cells ~17 and ~2 μm away from each other
407 [14], suggesting that yeast cells interact efficiently when they are 17 μm away from each
408 other. Similar interaction distances (3.2-12.1 μm) were found by Dal Co *et al.* when they
409 grew bidirectionally cross-feeding *E. coli* cells in a microfluidic chamber [13]. Our data
410 however show that in a three-dimensional environment with a metabolite-sink the interaction
411 distances are shorter, as producers and receivers ~15 μm away from each other could not
412 cross-feed (Figure 2D). Within aggregates cross-feeding was possible, but it was still less
413 efficient than what was achieved in presence of high concentrations of the secreted
414 metabolite (Figure 2B and 2F).

415 These results match the model prediction that interaction distances in three-dimensional
416 systems are shorter than in two-dimensional systems. It furthermore indicates that the
417 presence of a metabolite-sink also affects the interaction distance. In the set-ups of Dalco *et*
418 *al.* and Diener *et al.* the metabolite is degraded/consumed only by the receiver itself, so the
419 metabolite concentration will only decrease close to receiver cells. When receivers compete
420 with other metabolite-sinks, such as competing metabolite consumers or a dilute system, the
421 overall metabolite concentration will be lowered, resulting in shorter interaction distances.
422 Indeed, Koschwanez *et al.* showed that at low cell densities and low sucrose concentrations,
423 where the volume acts as the main metabolite-sink, *S. cerevisiae* cannot grow, even though
424 invertase splits sucrose into glucose and fructose in the periplasmic space, so very close to the
425 receiver cell [8].

426

427 In the presence of a competing metabolite-sink the concentration of the exchanged metabolite
428 is low, and we therefore expected that variation in the receivers' import affinity would
429 influence the interaction efficiency. However, within aggregates we observed only small
430 differences in growth of high and low affinity receivers (Figure 3), suggesting that dense

431 micro-colonies with a low diffusion rate were formed (supplementary information, section
432 4.1). Aggregating cells therefore seem to kill two birds with one stone: they decrease both the
433 cell-to-cell distance and the diffusion rate, two factors which were previously reported to
434 promote interaction [15, 34]. The resulting increase of the local concentration might also
435 explain why Koschwanez *et al.* saw that yeast cells which could not grow on low sucrose
436 concentrations due to their low cell density, could grow when the same amount of cells was
437 aggregated [8].

438 In our set-up the local glucose concentration increases with time, because the producers grew
439 independently from the receivers. Future research could focus on bidirectional cross-feeding
440 systems, where producer growth is limited by receiver growth. In that case the initial
441 production rate will be lower and receiver affinity might play a bigger role.

442

443 Controlled metabolite exchange is a critical feature of living cells [35], and forms the basis
444 for extracellular metabolism of nutrients and interactions with other cells. Concentration
445 gradients constrain the distance over which these interactions can occur and it therefore
446 shaped the evolution of the molecular mechanisms involved in these interactions. Slow
447 diffusion of large, aggregated resources like particulate iron ($>0.4 \mu\text{m}$) can for instance cause
448 cellular iron uptake to become diffusion limited. It is therefore hypothesized that cells secrete
449 siderophores to form fast diffusing iron-siderophore complexes after iron dissolution, in this
450 way increasing their iron uptake rate [36]. It is furthermore known that many extracellular
451 substrate-degrading enzymes are attached to the cell, which places the source (enzyme) close
452 to the receiver (cell). Invertase is for instance located in the periplasmic space of *S. cerevisiae*
453 [37], the protease of *L. lactis* is attached to the cell wall [9] and in both fungi and bacteria
454 cellulosomes are also attached to the cell wall [38]. Hauert *et al.* argue that when a producer
455 also benefits from its own product, which is the case for extracellular enzymes, spatially

456 structured localization of cells is only advantageous when the enzyme production costs are
457 high [39]. Attachment of extracellular enzymes to the cell wall therefore suggests that these
458 enzymes are costly, and indeed, Bachmann *et al.* showed in *L. lactis* that protease negative
459 strains outcompeted protease positive strains with a cell wall bound protease, unless they
460 were >1 mm apart (cell density of 10^3 cells/mL) [9].

461 In the presence of a competing public good-sink interacting cells can aggregate, for example
462 in biofilms, to reduce the diffusion distance and diffusion rate [40], which increases the
463 efficiency of their interactions [15, 34]. During evolution of cooperation in which costly
464 compounds are secreted, wildtype non-cooperators typically form such a competing public
465 good-sink, indicating that cell-to-cell distances well below 15 μm are required to evolve
466 costly cooperation. However, aggregation is not always increasing interaction efficiency,
467 because it also slows down the diffusion of inhibiting metabolic end-products from the
468 micro-colony and the diffusion of extracellular nutrients into the micro-colony. Aggregation
469 of the cross-feeding yoghurt consortium (*Lactobacillus bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus*
470 *thermophilus*) in 100-300 μm capsules reduced for instance their growth and acidification
471 rates, and proteolysis was only faster in the first hour [41], indicating that in this case the
472 aggregation costs did not outweigh the benefits. Aggregation also allows (evolution of)
473 contact-dependent transfer mechanisms, like nanotubes or vesicle chains. To our knowledge
474 *L. lactis* does not exchange cytosolic material using these contact-dependent transfer
475 mechanisms and the model indicates that just diffusion can explain our experimental results.
476

477 Consequences of concentration gradient constraints are not limited to bacteria and yeasts.
478 Plants, fungi and other (organisms with) large cells use intracellular concentration gradients
479 to regulate amongst others cell polarity, cell division and cell size [42–44]. Although the rate
480 of diffusion in the cytoplasm is fast, cells can use spatially structured protein modification

481 systems as source or sink, to create concentration gradients [45, 46]. It is therefore important
482 to think about the constraints - and opportunities - that concentration gradients may impose
483 on cellular interactions, how it shaped their evolution and their role in microbial consortia,
484 and how researchers can use these principles to understand and steer these processes.
485

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496

497 **Author contributions**

498 R.J.v.T., B.T. and H.B. conceived the study, designed experiments, interpreted the data and

499 wrote the paper. R.J.v.T., I.v.S. and E.Z. carried out the experiments. T.R. and A.L.

500 developed the aggregation protocol. C.P. and R.J.v.T. built the COMSOL Multiphysics

501 model. J.A.H. and O.P.K. constructed the strains *L. lactis* NZ9000_PTSman_GFP, *L. lactis*

502 NZ9000_PTScel_GFP and *L. lactis* NZ9000_glcU_GFP. All authors helped improving the

503 manuscript.

504

505 **Competing interests statement**

506 H.B. is also employed by NIZO Food Research, a contract research organization. NIZO Food

507 Research had no role in the study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or

508 preparation of the manuscript.

509

510 **Supplementary information**

511 **Section 1: Agarose bead size- and volume-distributions**

512 We prepared agarose beads surrounded by oil and made pictures with a microscope (9 per
513 emulsion, Figure S1A shows an example). Pictures were subsequently analyzed with ImageJ
514 to identify the beads (Figure S1B), and to measure size- and volume distributions (Figure
515 S1C and S1D). Small droplets were not always identified, but as they contain only little
516 volume this only marginally affects the analysis. Beads on the edge of the picture were
517 excluded from the analysis. Formed emulsions were polydisperse but distributions of
518 replicates were reproducible, with mean volume \pm SEM of 26 ± 2 pL (diameter of $37\ \mu\text{m}$).

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539 **Figure S1. Agarose bead size and volume.** (A) An example microscope picture of agarose beads.

540 (B) Agarose beads identified in (A) after ImageJ analysis. (C and D) Agarose bead size (C) and

541 volume (D) distribution (n=10 emulsions, 9 pictures per emulsion).

542

543 **Section 2: 10^9 *L. lactis* MG1363 cells/mL as competing glucose-consumers**

544 To establish if addition of 10^9 *L. lactis* MG1363 cells per mL outside agarose beads
545 prevented cross-talk between beads, we mixed beads with producers and beads with receivers
546 and incubated them in presence of lactose in different spatial structures (Figure S2). After
547 incubation surrounded by oil only producers were grown, which was expected as glucose
548 could not diffuse from beads. When glucose could diffuse from beads and no *L. lactis*
549 MG1363 cells were added outside the beads, both producers and receivers grew. However, in
550 presence of 10^9 *L. lactis* MG1363 cells per mL outside the agarose beads only producers
551 grew, suggesting that glucose leaving beads with producers was mainly consumed by
552 *L. lactis* MG1363 cells outside the beads and did not reach receivers in neighboring beads.
553 The glucose concentration outside the beads probably did not exceed the low micro-molar
554 range, as the K_m for glucose of the highest affinity transporter in *L. lactis* MG1363 is 13 μ M
555 [22] and the *L. lactis* MG1363 cell density was high.

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No diffusion from beads

Diffusion from beads

no competing glucose-consumers

competing glucose-consumers

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Figure S2: Addition of *L. lactis* MG1363 outside agarose beads prevents cross-talk between beads. Agarose beads with producers and agarose beads with receivers were mixed and incubated in three different spatial structures: surrounded by oil (no diffusion from beads, n=3), surrounded by CDM without *L. lactis* MG1363 (no competing glucose-consumers, n=3) and surrounded by CDM with 10^9 single *L. lactis* MG1363 cells per mL (competing glucose-consumers, n=3). Histograms show the fluorescence/scatter ratio of the populations that were gated as “growth”.

577 **Section 3: Flow cytometry gating strategy and data analysis**

578 Figure S3 shows the flow cytometry gating strategy and data analysis procedure.

579

580

581 **Overview: Raw data after incubation**

588 **Step 1. Gate the filled agarose beads**

*This step is excluded for samples containing agarose beads with only GFP- cells

596 **Step 2. Separate beads with and beads without growth**

603 **Step 3. Calculate fluorescence/scatter ratio**

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- 605
- Subtract the mean side scatter and fluorescence before incubation from the side scatter and fluorescence after incubation (background correction)
 - Calculate the ratio between the corrected fluorescence and side scatter to identify which celltypes were grown inside the agarose beads

606 **Figure S3. Flow cytometry gating strategy and data analysis.**

607 **Overview.** Each agarose bead sample was measured twice. We first acquired an overview of the
608 complete sample, containing both single cells and agarose beads. Drawn gates were based on
609 measurements of empty agarose beads and single cells. Thereafter we used an increased forward and
610 side scatter threshold to leave out most of the single cells, this data was used for gating and data
611 analysis. **Step 1.** Beads containing cells (“filled beads”) were gated by including the largest agarose
612 beads and excluding the noise and the empty agarose beads. For the control samples with only
613 producers empty beads were not excluded, because before incubation agarose beads with GFP-
614 producers could not be separated from empty beads. **Step 2.** Beads with and without growth were
615 separated with a forward scatter threshold. This threshold was set for each sample individually, based
616 on the forward scatter before incubation. This stringent gating might underestimate the amount of
617 beads with growth, but it ensures that beads without growth are excluded from analysis. **Step 3.** The
618 side scatter and fluorescence were background-corrected based on their values before incubation. The
619 distribution of fluorescence/scatter ratios of background-corrected data is plotted to identify which
620 cell-types were grown inside the agarose beads.

621

622 **Section 4: Reaction-diffusion model in COMSOL Multiphysics**

623 **4.1 Geometry of the agarose bead model**

624 Figure S4 shows the geometry of agarose bead model.

625

644 **Figure S4: Model geometry implemented in COMSOL Multiphysics.** (A) An agarose bead (sphere
 645 with diameter of 40 μm) contains 8 receiver cells and 0 or 1 producer cells. Each cell is a sphere with
 646 a diameter of 1 μm. Within the agarose bead receivers are placed at the virtual corners of a cube, and
 647 the producer in the middle. The distance between the surface of producers and receivers is either 0 or
 648 15 μm. (B and C) An agarose bead with one producer (bead 1) and an agarose bead without a
 649 producer (bead 2) are placed in a cube of 100 μm (corresponding to $2 \cdot 10^6$ beads/mL). In (B) the
 650 distance between the producer and receiver is 15 μm, in (C) they are in contact (0 μm). Producers and
 651 receivers in contact are placed in a micro-colony (sphere with a diameter of 4 μm) with a reduced
 652 diffusion coefficient ($D_{\text{eff},s}$).

653

654 **4.2 Reaction-diffusion model and parameter values**

655 *Material balance.* The spatial distribution (x,y,z) and change in time (t) of the concentration
656 C_s (mol/m³) of glucose in the bead and surrounding liquid resulted from solving the partial
657 differential equation which balances the diffusion rate with a reaction rate r_s :

$$\frac{\partial C_s}{\partial t} = D_s \left(\frac{\partial^2 C_s}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 C_s}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 C_s}{\partial z^2} \right) + r_s$$

658

659 *Diffusion.* The same diffusion coefficient of glucose, D_s (m²/s), was used outside and inside
660 the agarose beads. It was set to the value of D_s in water [29], because D_s in agarose gels is
661 similar to that in water [30]. The effective diffusion coefficient in micro-colonies depends on
662 the void fraction, i.e. volume not occupied by cells per total micro-colony volume, and the
663 tortuosity [13, 40]. Cells growing in an agarose matrix form dense colonies, therefore the
664 effective diffusion coefficient within the colonies ($D_{\text{eff},s}$) was set to 10% of the diffusion
665 coefficient in water (D_s) [29, 31].

666

667 *Reaction.* The net glucose rate r_s (mol/m³/s) results as the difference between production and
668 consumption at a certain position in space, $r_s = q_p C_x - q_s C_x$. The specific glucose production
669 rate (q_p) of *L. lactis* NZ9000 Glc-Lac+ is the same as its specific lactose uptake rate, as each
670 lactose molecule contains one glucose molecule. The q_p was therefore set to a constant value
671 of 1 molP/CmolX/h [47] and applied within the producer cells. Simulations which did include
672 the lactose concentration and Monod kinetics for lactose consumption yielded similar results
673 as simulations with a constant q_p , therefore we adopted the simpler constant rate. For
674 receivers the glucose uptake was assumed with a saturation (Monod) kinetics,
675 $q_s = q_s^{\text{max}} \cdot C_s / (K_s + C_s)$. We used the K_s of the highest affinity glucose transporter of *L. lactis*
676 MG1363 [22], and q_s^{max} was set to 1 molS/CmolX/h [48]. To calculate the biomass
677 concentration C_x (CmolX/m³) we assumed a molecular weight of biomass of 24.6 grams per

678 Cmol dry biomass ($\text{CH}_{1.8}\text{O}_{0.5}\text{N}_{0.2}$) [49, 50], a cellular water content of 70 wt% [51] and a
679 cellular density of 1000 g/L [51]. These values lead to a glucose production or maximal
680 glucose consumption rate of 38 mol/m³/s. A competing glucose-consumer was modelled by
681 adding glucose consumption outside agarose beads with the same Monod kinetics as that of
682 receivers. Cell growth was not incorporated in the model.

683

684 *Boundaries.* The concentration at the agarose bead surface was based on a partition
685 coefficient which was set to 0 when incubation in oil was modelled, and to 1 for incubation in
686 CDM. The liquid domain (cube) boundaries were insulated (no-flux boundary condition).

687

688 *Parameters.* Table S1 lists the default parameters used in the COMSOL Multiphysics model
689 with sources for their values.

690

691 **Table S1: Default parameter values of the COMSOL Multiphysics model**

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Source
Maximum specific uptake rate of glucose	q_s^{\max}	38 mol/m ³ /s	[48]
Specific production rate of glucose	q_p	38 mol/m ³ /s	[47]
Half-saturation (Monod) coefficient	K_s	0.01 mM	[22]
Diffusion coefficient in water and agarose beads	D_s	$6.7 \cdot 10^{-10}$ m ² /s	[29]
Effective diffusion coefficient in micro-colonies	$D_{\text{eff},s}$	$0.1 \cdot D_s$	[29, 31]

692

693 **4.3 Predicted concentration gradients in two- and three-dimensional reaction-diffusion** 694 **systems**

695 To analyze the difference in concentration gradients in two- and three-dimensional systems
696 we modelled production by one producer cell in two different geometries, as represented in
697 Figure S5. In the two-dimensional system the model predicts that the product concentration is

698 halved at 24 μm from the producer, whereas in the three-dimensional system this happens at
699 only 0.6 μm .

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713 **Figure S5: Predicted concentration gradients in two- and three-dimensional reaction-diffusion**

714 **systems.** A producer cell with a diameter of 1 μm was placed in the middle of a very thin rectangular

715 block (1.1 μm thickness) to represent a quasi-two-dimensional system. For the three-dimensional

716 system it was placed in the middle of a cube. For the cube, concentrations at the cube boundaries were

717 set to zero. For the thin plate the concentrations at the four lateral faces were set to zero, and the

718 top and bottom boundaries were insulated (no-flux boundary condition). The total volume of

719 both systems was 1 nL ($1 \cdot 10^6$ cells/mL). A time dependent study in COMSOL Multiphysics

720 yielded concentration gradients at several moments. The figure shows the concentrations

721 along the diagonal after 5 hours.

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724 **4.4 Sensitivity analysis for q_p and q_s^{\max}**

725 Figure S6 shows the predicted glucose concentration (Figure S6A) and glucose production
726 rate (Figure S6B) over a plane crossing the producer cell and four of the eight receiver cells.
727 Profiles for aggregated cells and for cells $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$ away from each other are shown. Because
728 it is difficult to know the actual q_p and q_s^{\max} inside agarose beads, we also performed a
729 sensitivity analysis (Figure S7). A 5-fold change in q_p and q_s^{\max} resulted in similar
730 concentration gradients and it did not affect our hypotheses.

A. Glucose concentration

B. Glucose production rate

755 **Figure S6: Predicted glucose concentration (A) and glucose production rates (B) in agarose**
756 **beads surrounded by CDM.** The glucose concentration (A) and the glucose production rate (B) are
757 plotted over a plane crossing the producer cell and four of the eight receiver cells. Profiles for
758 aggregated cells and for cells $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$ away from each other are shown.

778 **Figure S7: Predicted concentration gradients after varying q_p and q_s^{max} .** q_p and q_s^{max} were
779 increased and decreased five-fold and the effects on the predicted concentration gradients in different
780 spatial structures are shown.

781

782 **4.5 Model predictions for the glucose uptake of receivers with different affinities**

783 We analyzed the effect of the glucose affinity of receivers on their ability to utilize the
784 glucose made by the producer. To model the individual glucose transporters of *L. lactis*
785 MG1363 in COMSOL the K_s values as reported by Castro *et al.* were used [22]. For *L. lactis*
786 NZ9000_GFP_glcU the q_s^{\max} was reduced with a factor four, which reflects the differences in
787 V_{\max} of the transporters [22]. We calculated the glucose uptake for the different mutants after
788 5 hours in presence of competing glucose-consumers, without considering growth of the cells
789 (Figure S8). The effective diffusion coefficient ($D_{\text{eff},s}$) varies from 10-70%, depending on the
790 density of the micro-colony [29, 31]. Figure S7 shows the glucose uptake when $D_{\text{eff},s}$ is 10%,
791 30% and 70%. We included a sensitivity analysis for five-fold changes in q_p and q_s^{\max} values,
792 which all showed similar trends as the reference (1x q_p and 1x q_s^{\max}).

793

811 **Figure S8: Predicted glucose uptake.** We modelled receiver cells with different glucose affinities
812 and calculated the predicted glucose uptake. A sensitivity analysis for five-fold changes in q_p and q_s^{\max}
813 values was incorporated. Each simulation contained eight receiver cells aggregated with a producer
814 (Figure S5), this figure shows the combined glucose uptake of these receivers.
815

816 **Section 5: Growth rate determination**

817 Strains were incubated in CDM + 0.2 wt% glucose in a 96-well plate. The OD₆₀₀ was
818 measured every six minutes for 24 hours using a SPECTRAMax 384 plus plate reader
819 (Molecular Devices, San Jose, CA, USA). OD₆₀₀ measurements were background corrected,
820 ln-transformed and the slope of the region with exponential growth was calculated as the
821 growth rate (Table S2).

822

823 **Table S2. Growth rates of receivers with different glucose transporters (n=22).**

Strain	Growth rate ± SD (h⁻¹)
<i>L. lactis</i> MG1363_GFP	1.25 ± 0.04
<i>L. lactis</i> NZ9000_GFP_glcU	0.79 ± 0.04
<i>L. lactis</i> NZ9000_GFP_PTSman	0.74 ± 0.11
<i>L. lactis</i> NZ9000_GFP_PTScel	0.57 ± 0.03

824

825 **Section 6: Flow cytometry data for receivers glucose transporters with different**
826 **affinities and V_{\max}**

827 We constitutively expressed GFP in three previously constructed *L. lactis* NZ9000 mutants
828 with a single glucose transporter [27], and analyzed their growth in different spatial
829 structures. This experiment focused on beads incubated in CDM (allowing glucose diffusion
830 from beads), as we expected that under these conditions the transporter characteristics of
831 receivers would be important. Figure S9A shows the experimental results when receivers
832 were ~15 μm from a producer within the same bead and incubated in CDM, whereas in
833 Figure S9B the beads were incubated in medium with 10^9 glucose-consumers per mL. Figure
834 S9C shows the experimental results of producer-receiver aggregates, incubated in CDM with
835 10^9 glucose-consumers per mL. Without a competing glucose-consumers we observed
836 growth of both receivers with and receivers without a producer in their bead (Figure S9A),
837 while with competing glucose-consumers only producers could grow (Figure S9B). In
838 producer-receiver aggregates receivers were able to grow, despite the presence of competing
839 glucose-consumers (Figure S9C). The results were similar for all glucose transporters, and
840 were consistent with the results of the wild-type (Figure 2, Table 2).

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Figure S9A. Glucose accumulates, allowing receivers to grow independent of the available glucose transporter. See complete caption on page 24.

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893 **Figure S9B.** In presence of competing glucose-consumers receivers cannot grow, independent of the
894 available glucose transporter. See complete caption on page 24.

919 **Figure S9C.** Despite the presence of competing glucose-consumers receivers within producer-
 920 receiver aggregates can grow, independently of the available glucose transporter. See complete
 921 caption on page 24.

922 **Figure S9: Response of consortia containing receivers with different glucose affinities.** The
923 forward scatter histograms show the percentage of beads that were gated as “growth” in the co-culture
924 of producer and receivers. The fluorescence/scatter histograms show the fluorescence/scatter ratio of
925 beads that were gated as “growth” (n=3). Next to the co-culture of producer and receivers several
926 control samples are included: receivers only, producers only and co-cultures of non-producers and
927 receivers (n=3 for each of them). The non-producers and receivers, and the producers only controls
928 are overlapping in all plots. The schematic drawing at the right shows the situation after growth, based
929 on data from the two histograms. **Different panels contain different spatial structures:** (A)
930 Receivers ~15 μm from a producer within the same bead, incubated in CDM. (B) Receivers ~15 μm
931 from a producer within the same bead, incubated in CDM with 10^9 glucose-consumers per mL. (C)
932 Aggregates of producers and receivers, incubated in beads surrounded by CDM with 10^9 glucose-
933 consumers per mL.
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